

COBALT PHOSPHIDES COATED COPPER OXIDE NANOROD ARRAYS FOR ENHANCED OVERALL WATER SPLITTING

T. L. L. Doan¹, D. T. Tran¹, K. R. Park¹, N. H. Kim^{1*}, J. H. Lee^{1,2*}

¹ Advanced Materials Institute for BIN Convergence Technology (BK21 Plus Global Program), Department of BIN Convergence Technology, Chonbuk National University, Jeonju, Jeonbuk, 54896, Republic of Korea

² Carbon Composite Research Center, Department of Polymer-Nano Science and Technology, Chonbuk National University, Jeonju, Jeonbuk, 54896, Republic of Korea

* Corresponding author (nhk@chonbuk.ac.kr and jhl@chonbuk.ac.kr)

Keywords: Cobalt phosphide, Copper oxide, Electrocatalysts, Water splitting.

ABSTRACT

Although water splitting has been recognized as a clean energy technology for producing pure hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂), the sluggish kinetics of cathode hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and anode oxygen evolution reaction (OER) extremely hinder its practical application. Herein, we report the cost-effective fabrication of cobalt phosphides coated copper oxide nanorod arrays supported 3D foam (Co₂P@CuO NR/CF) as an efficient electrocatalyst for overall water splitting in alkaline condition. The obtained Co₂P@CuO NR/CF demonstrated highly catalytic activity for both HER and OER. It only required a small overpotential of 108 mA cm⁻¹ for HER and 270 mA cm⁻¹ for OER to achieve the current density of 10 mA cm⁻² with a low Tafel slope of 69 and 74 mV dec⁻¹, respectively. Notably, Co₂P@CuO NR/CF exhibited excellently stable properties, which resulted in continually producing H₂ and/or O₂ at least 30 h with maintaining a steady current density of 10 mA cm⁻². This considerable catalytic activity resulted from the large surface area, fast electron transfer and open-channel of 3D core-shell structure, and the synergetic effect between the CuO core and the Co₂P shell. Our research is expected to provide a promising strategy to develop efficient HER and OER electrocatalyst towards large-scale practical water splitting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the use of traditional fossil fuels has caused many issues to environment and living quality. Therefore, the research on sustainable and eco-friendly energies, such as solar energy, wind energy, and hydrogen energy.... to replace the natural resources are highly imperative. Hydrogen as a clean, renewable, environmentally friendly, and sustainable energy source has been considered as promising ideal energy for future [1]. There are various methods for the synthesis of pure hydrogen. Among those, splitting of water offers has been emerging as a simple and cost-effective way to produce hydrogen on a large-scale. However, the high energy barrier of cathodic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and the sluggish kinetic of anodic oxygen evolution reaction (OER) required to develop highly efficient electrocatalyst for water splitting [2, 3]. So far, Pt-based and IrO₂/RuO₂-based catalysts have been known as the most efficient electrocatalysts for HER and OER, respectively. Unfortunately, the high cost, scarcity, and low stability hinder their practical applications as well as their efficiency under the long-term operation condition. In last few decades, earth-abundant transition metals have attracted a lot of attention for designing electrocatalysts to simultaneously accelerate HER and OER due to their low cost, desirable catalytic activity and stability. Among them, cobalt-based catalysts such as Co oxides/hydroxides, Co sulfides, Co nitride, Co phosphides (CoPs) with earth-abundant source, inexpensiveness, and low energy barrier of H adsorption appeared as the promising candidates for HER and OER [4]. Notably, because CoPs possess the combined advantages of excellent electrical conductivity, electrochemical/chemical stability, low energy barrier of H adsorption, and low cost, the numerous of studies have been employed them as active transition metal-based catalysts for water splitting [5-7]. For example, Jin et al. reported that Co₂P nanowires as advanced bifunctional electrocatalysts for overall water splitting [8]. In another study, Liu et al.

developed self-standing CoP nanosheets supported on carbon cloth as an efficient electrocatalyst for water splitting with low OER, HER overpotential of 300 and 145 mV at 10 mA cm⁻¹, respectively [9]. Zhou et al. presented two-dimensional ultrathin arrays of CoP as outstanding active and stable electrocatalyst toward both half-reaction in overall water splitting [10]. However, the low catalytic activity of CoPs due to easy agglomeration and poor conductivity is still a grand challenge. Recently, the heterostructures have been studied for both HER and OER because the synergistic effect of components can increase surface area, catalytic activity, as well as optimized activation energy [11]. Benefiting from the advantage of the heterostructures, the designing of CoPs-based heterostructures has been considered as efficient approach to improve catalytic activity of CoPs. Three-dimensional (3D) CuO nanorod arrays owing to good properties and outstanding structure demonstrated that an open-channel and large surface area of 3D structure to provide more active sites for the diffusion of gas/electrolyte, which resulted in enhancing efficient electron transfer and improving catalytic activity [12, 13]. Besides, the CuO nanostructures with their abundance, low cost, and easy synthesis have been reported as photoelectrochemical catalysts and electrochemical catalysts for HER and OER. Based on the above comments, it is expected that the fabrication heterostructures of CoPs and CuO nanorod arrays supported on 3D copper foam can avoid the agglomeration of CoPs as well as improve the conductive property of both CoPs and CuO, thereby displaying as an efficient electrocatalyst for overall water splitting.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Synthesis of 3D Cu(OH)₂ NR/CF

Firstly, a piece of Cu foam (1 cm x 5 cm) was cleaned in acetone, ethanol, acetic acid, and water by sonication for 15 min each to remove the surface oxides and impurities. Following this, the pre-cleaned Cu foam was rapidly immersed in a solution containing 1.513g (NH₄)₂S₂O₈, 5.1024 g NaOH, and 50 mL distilled water (DI water) at room temperature for 15 min. Finally, the Cu foam with blue color due to the growth of Cu(OH)₂ NR was rinsed with DI water several times to remove the remaining sodium hydroxide until its pH=7 and dried at 60 °C for 12h in oven.

Scheme1: Scheme illustration of the synthesis of Co₂P@CuO NR/CF.

2.2 Synthesis of Co₃O₄@CuO NR/CF

A piece of the resulting Cu(OH)₂ NR/CF was immersed into an aqueous solution with 1.09g Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and 40 mL distilled water under slow stirring for 90 min. Subsequently, the obtained material was continued to immerse into 40 mL 1 M NaOH solution under slow stirring for 45 min to obtain Co(OH)₂@Cu(OH)₂ NR/CF. After washing several times to remove the remaining sodium hydroxide by distilled water, the product was dried at 60 °C overnight. To prepare Co₃O₄@CuO

NR/CF, the resulting $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2@\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2/\text{CF}$ were placed in a quartz boat and annealed at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h in air condition with a heating rate of $5\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$.

2.3 Synthesis of $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$

NaH_2PO_2 was used as phosphorus source to synthesize Co_2P supported on $\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$. A piece of resulting $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$ (1 cm x 5 cm) and 440 mg NaH_2PO_2 were placed at two sides of quartz tube, in which NaH_2PO_2 was placed on the upstream side of the quartz tube. The sample was then heated to $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h with a heating rate of $2\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ under Ar atmosphere (10 sccm). After finishing the heating process, the product was naturally cooled down to room temperature (scheme 1).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphological and structural characterization

The FE-SEM measurements were performed to confirm the surface morphology of samples. The SEM images of Cu foam (Figs. 1a and b) showed a 3D structure with high porosity and flat surface full of grain boundaries. Whereas, The SEM images of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$ (Figs. 1c and d) exhibited that the dense array of $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}$ fully covered on the surface of copper foam and each nanorod is considered as one-dimensional structure that directly connects to surface of substrate. In addition, the EDX analysis (inset Fig. 1d) clearly indicated the corresponding peaks for Cu, Co, P and O elements, confirming the formation of $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}$ on 3D copper foam substrate.

Figure 1: SEM image of (a, b) copper foam and (c, d) $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$.

3.2 Electrocatalytic activity towards HER and OER

The electrocatalytic properties of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$ electrode towards HER was firstly investigated in N_2 -saturated 1M KOH aqueous electrolyte at scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . The comparison of LSV curves in Figure 2a presents that the $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$ electrode exhibited an efficient HER catalyst in alkaline solution with much better catalytic activity than $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{CuO NR}$, $\text{Co}_2\text{P}/\text{CF}$, $\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$, and pure CF. Figure 2b shows the corresponding overpotentials for these catalysts, which needs to achieve current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} and -50 mA cm^{-2} . The pure CF showed the poorly catalytic activity toward HER with overpotential of 377.4 mV at current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} . Meanwhile, to achieve current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} , the 195.4, 261.4 and 295.4 mV overpotentials were required for $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$, $\text{Co}_2\text{P}/\text{CF}$ and $\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$, respectively. In contrast, the $\text{Co}_2\text{P}@\text{CuO NR}/\text{CF}$ the requirement of overpotential of 108 mV at current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} . The overpotential value of both $\text{CuO NN}/\text{CF}$ and $\text{Co}_2\text{P}/\text{CF}$ were much higher than the overpotential

value of $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ at current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} , implying that the important factor for enhancing the electrocatalytic activity was the synergic effects between the CuO core and Co_2P shell. To further understand catalytic kinetics of electrocatalysts, the Tafel plot for HER of $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@CuO NR/CF}$, $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$, CuO NR/CF, bare CF, and Pt/C were recorded (Fig. 2c). Pt/C provided the lowest Tafel slope value of 52.5 mV dec^{-1} compared to other electrodes. The Tafel slope value of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ is 69.4 mV dec^{-1} , which is lower than $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@CuO NR/CF}$ (99.1 mV dec^{-1}), $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$ (151 mV dec^{-1}), CuO NR/CF (165 mV dec^{-1}), and bare CF (206 mV dec^{-1}), demonstrating the good kinetics of this catalyst for HER with a Volmer-Heyrovsky mechanism. The durability of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalyst and Pt/C for HER was carried out at constant current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} for 30 h (Fig. 2d). We can see that the overpotential of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalyst is almost unincreased after 30 h, whereas the overpotential of the Pt/C seems to unstable after few hours.

Figure 2: Hydrogen evolution reaction electrocatalysis in KOH 1M. (a) LSV curve of the Pt/C on CF, $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@CuO NR/CF}$, $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$, CuO NR/CF and pure Cu foam at scan rate for 5 mV s^{-1} . (b) The comparison of overpotential at current density of -10 and -50 mA cm^{-2} for the corresponding electrocatalysts. (c) Corresponding the Tafel plot of the electrocatalysts. (d) Long-term stability curve recorded from Pt/C on CF, $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ at constant current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} for 30 h.

The electrocatalytic properties of electrodes toward OER was investigated in N_2 -saturated 1 M KOH electrolyte. Figure 3a presents the LSV curves of $\text{Ru}_2\text{O}_3/\text{C}$ on CF, CuO NR/CF, $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@CuO NR/CF}$, and $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalysts toward OER. Interesting, the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalyst revealed the highest catalytic activity with the demand overpotential of only 270 mV to obtain the current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} (Fig. 3b). This overpotential value is lower than the overpotential of the $\text{Ru}_2\text{O}_3/\text{C}$ on CF (290 mV). The requiring overpotential of the CuO NR/CF, $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$, and $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@CuO NR/CF}$ for current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} were 310, 320, and 350 mV, respectively, suggesting that the catalytic efficiency of these electrodes is lower than $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalyst. Figure 3c shows the corresponding Tafel plot of these catalysts. The Tafel slope value of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ is 74.4 mV dec^{-1} , which smaller than those for $\text{Ru}_2\text{O}_3/\text{C}$ (83.5 mV dec^{-1}), $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@CuO NR/CF}$ (94.8 mV dec^{-1}), CuO NR/CF (128 mV dec^{-1}), $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$ (167 mV dec^{-1}), and pure CF (374 mV dec^{-1}), meaning that the discharge process as well as favorable catalytic kinetics during OER of $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ was highest among all catalysts. Besides, the long-term electrochemical durability of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ electrode was further probed by recording long-term stability for 30 h (Fig. 3d). The result

indicated the excellent durability of the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ towards OER as compared with RuO_2/C on CF.

Figure 3: (a) LSV curve of the RuO_2/C on CF, $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{CuO NR/CF}$, $\text{Co}_2\text{P/CF}$, CuO NR/CF and pure Cu foam at scan rate for 5 mV s^{-1} . (b) The comparison of overpotential at current density of 10 and 50 mA cm^{-2} for the corresponding electrocatalysts. (c) Corresponding the Tafel plot of the electrocatalysts. (d) Long-term stability curve recorded from RuO_2/C on CF, $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ at constant current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} for 30 h.

4 CONCLUSIONS

For the first time, Co_2P supported on CuO nanorod arrays were in-situ fabricated on three-dimensional (3D) copper foam ($\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$) by a simple method for effective overall water splitting. The resulting $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalyst showed high electrocatalytic activity towards HER with a low overpotential of 108 mV to acquire current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} in alkaline media. In addition, the $\text{Co}_2\text{P@CuO NR/CF}$ catalyst was also demonstrated as an efficient OER with an overpotential of 270 mV at current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} . The achieved results suggest a novel advanced electrocatalyst with efficient activity, stability, low-cost, and large-scale production for water splitting technology.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support from the Nano-Material Technology Development Program (2016M3A7B4900117) and the Basic Research Program (2017R1A2B3004917) through the National Research Foundation (NRF) funded by the Ministry of Science and ICT, Republic of Korea.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Jiao, Y. Zheng, M. Jaroniec and S. Z. Qiao, Design of electrocatalysts for oxygen-and hydrogen-involving energy conversion reactions, *Chemical Society Reviews*, **44**, 2015, pp. 2060-2086 (doi: [10.1039/C4CS00470A](https://doi.org/10.1039/C4CS00470A)).
- [2] H. Jin, J. Wang, D. Su, Z. Wei, Z. Pang and Y. Wang, In-situ cobalt-cobalt oxide/N-doped carbon hybrids as superior bifunctional electrocatalysts for hydrogen and oxygen evolution, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **137**, 2015, pp. 2688-2694 (doi: [10.1021/ja5127165](https://doi.org/10.1021/ja5127165)).

- [3] Y. Liang, Y. Li, H. Wang, J. Zhou, J. Wang, T. Regier and H. Dai, Co₃O₄ nanocrystals on graphene as a synergistic catalyst for oxygen reduction reaction, *Nature Materials*, **10**, 2011, pp. 780–786 (doi: [10.1038/nmat3087](https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat3087)).
- [4] P. Du and R. Eisenberg, Catalysts made of earth-abundant elements (Co, Ni, Fe) for water splitting: Recent progress and future challenges, *Energy & Environmental Science*, **5**, 2012, pp. 6012-6021 (doi: [10.1039/C2EE03250C](https://doi.org/10.1039/C2EE03250C)).
- [5] E. J. Popczun, C. G. Read, C. W. Roske, N. S. Lewis and R. E. Schaak, Highly active electrocatalysis of the hydrogen evolution reaction by cobalt phosphide nanoparticles, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, **53**, 2014, pp. 1-5 (doi: [10.1002/anie.201402646](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201402646)).
- [6] J. Tian, N. Cheng, Q. Liu, W. Xing and X. Sun, Cobalt phosphide nanowires: efficient nanostructures for fluorescence sensing of biomolecules and photocatalytic evolution of dihydrogen from water under visible light, *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, **54**, 2015, pp. 1-6 (doi: [10.1002/anie.201402646](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201402646)).
- [7] J. Wang, W. Cui, Q. Liu, Z. Xing, A. M. Asiri and X. Sun, Recent progress in cobalt-based heterogeneous catalysts for electrochemical water splitting, *Advanced Materials*, **28**, 2016, pp. 215-230 (doi: [10.1002/adma.201502696](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201502696)).
- [8] Z. Jin, P. Li and D. Xiao, Metallic Co₂P ultrathin nanowires distinguished from CoP as robust electrocatalysts for overall water-splitting, *Green Chemistry*, **18**, 2016, pp. 1459-1464 (doi: [10.1039/C5GC02462E](https://doi.org/10.1039/C5GC02462E)).
- [9] T. Liu, L. Xie, J. Yang, R. Kong, G. Du and A. M. Asiri, Self-standing CoP nanosheets array: a three-dimensional bifunctional catalyst electrode for overall water splitting in both neutral and alkaline media, *Chemelectrochem*, **4**, 2017, pp. 1840-1845 (doi: [10.1002/celec.201700392](https://doi.org/10.1002/celec.201700392)).
- [10] L. Zhou, M. Shao, J. Li, S. Jiang, M. Wei and X. Duan, Two-dimensional ultrathin arrays of CoP: electronic modulation toward high performance overall water splitting, *Nano Energy*, **41**, 2017, pp. 583-590 (doi: [10.1016/j.nanoen.2017.10.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2017.10.009)).
- [11] Q. Zhou, T-T. Li, J. Qian, Y. Hu, F. Guo and Y-Q. Zheng, Self-supported hierarchical CuOx@Co₃O₄ heterostructures as efficient bifunctional electrocatalysts for water splitting, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, **6**, 2018, pp. 14431-14439 (doi: [10.1039/C8TA03120G](https://doi.org/10.1039/C8TA03120G)).
- [12] M. Xie, L. Yang, Y. Ji, Z. Wang, X. Ren, Z. Liu, A. M. Asiri, X. Xiong and X. Sun, An amorphous Co-carbonate-hydroxide nanowire array for efficient and durable oxygen evolution reaction in carbonate electrolytes, *Nanoscale*, **9**, 2017, pp. 16612-16615 (doi: [10.1039/C7NR07269D](https://doi.org/10.1039/C7NR07269D)).
- [13] L. Yu, H. Zhou, J. Sun, F. Qin, F. Yu, J. Bao, Y. Yu, S. Chen and Z. Ren, Cu nanowires shelled with NiFe layered double hydroxide nanosheets as bifunctional electrocatalysts for overall water splitting, *Energy & Environmental Science*, **10**, 2017, pp. 1820-1827 (doi: [10.1039/C7EE01571B](https://doi.org/10.1039/C7EE01571B)).